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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A RP- HPLC
METHOD FOR THE BIO-ANALYSIS OF OXCARBAZEPINE IN
RAT PLASMA****N. Anjaneyulu***, R. Naga Kishore, M. Ravi Kumar, and D. Anil NaikDepartment of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Geethanjali College of Pharmacy, Cheeryal(V),
Keesara(M), Medchal (Dist), Telangana, India – 501301**Abstract**

A new plan was fixed for estimation of Oxcarbazepine by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic actions continue strongly grow for the break of Oxcarbazepine by applying Agilent C18 column (4.6×150mm) 5 μ , flow rate was 1.0 ml/min, mobile phase ratio was Di- potassium hydrogen phosphate: ACN (70:30% v/v) detection wavelength was 593nm. The instrument used was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The confinements times continue begin to be 2.954mins. The % pureness containing Oxcarbazepine was begin to be 99.87%.The system fitness parameters for Oxcarbazepine such as theoretical plates also tracking component were begin to be 4600, 1.2. The analytic plan was approve in agreement with ICH protocol (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Oxcarbazepine act begin in absorption area of 20 μ g-100 μ g and correlation coefficient (r^2) was begin to be 0.999, % recovery was begin to be 100.56%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.17, % RSD for transitional precision was 0.10. The precision study was precision, robustness also repeatability, LOD value was 0.303 and LOQ value was 1.011.

Keywords: Agilent C18, Oxcarbazepine, RP-HPLC, and Rat plasma.**Corresponding author:****N. Anjaneyulu,**Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
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INTRODUCTION:

Oxcarbazepine (OXETOL) is chemically **9-oxo-2-azatricyclo [9.4.0.0^{3, 8}] pentadeca- 1(15), 3, 5, 7, 11, 13-hexaene-2-carboxamide**. Trileptal is the brand name for the generic drug Oxcarbazepine, a prescription drug used to treat seizures and epilepsy in adults and children's over 2 years old. This is structural derivative of carbamazepine and Anti-convulsant drug primarily used in the treatment of epilepsy [1]. Oxcarbazepine is a prodrug which is activated to licarbazepine in the liver [2]. It helps to reduce the impact on the liver of metabolizing the drug and also prevents the serious forms of Anemia

or agranulocytosis, occasionally associated with carbamazepine [3]. Route of administration by mouth (tablets or liquids.) While half-life of Oxcarbazepine 1-5 hrs (Healthy adults) and Extraction through the Kidney. Oxcarbazepine is used alone or in combination with other medications for the treatment of focal (partial) seizures in adults. In pediatric populations, it can be used by itself for the treatment of partial seizures for children 4 years and older, or in combination with other medications for children 2 years and older. [4].

Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂

Molecular weight: 252.268
Chemical structure of Oxcarbazepine

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials and reagents: Oxcarbazepine, KH₂PO₄, K₂HPO₄, water, Di-potassium hydrogen phosphate, Methanol, Acetonitrile, Orthophosphoric acid,

Equipment: HPLC- HPLC-auto sampler –UV detector Separation module 2695, PDA detector Empower-software version-2 Waters, U.V double beam spectrometer, UV 3000+, U.V win soft ware, Lab India, Digital weighing balance (sensitivity 5mg), pH meter, Sonicator.

PREPARATION OF THE OXCARBAZEPINE STANDARD & SAMPLE SOLUTION:**Standard Solution Preparation:**

10 mg Amount of standard was mixed with 10 ml Acetonitrile to +2ml of rat plasma (untreated) then vertically shaken for 30 min then centrifuged at 5000rpm for 1 hr. Then it was filtered using membrane filters to get clear organic solution. Then it was filled in to the sample vials of HPLC and loaded

on to HPLC for Run.

Sample Solution Preparation:

Blood samples are collected from the animal's rats and then centrifuged at 5000rpm for 1 hr to separate the plasma from blood. Then the separated was mixed with Acetonitrile then loaded on to the HPLC for Run.

Method Development: The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10µg/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of Oxcarbazepine was obtained and Oxcarbazepine showed absorbance's maxima at 593nm. The spectrums are shown in Fig

Spectrum showing of Oxcarbazepine

The chromatographical methodology development for the estimation of Oxcarbazepine were optimized by many trials for numerous parameters as totally different column, rate of flow and mobile section, finally the subsequent chromatographical methodology was chosen for the separation and quantification of Oxcarbazepine in API and pharmaceutical dose kind by RP- HPLC methodology.

Mobile phase blank preparation (Chromatogram)

Chromatographic conditions (Optimised method)

Mobile phase : Di- potassium hydrogen phosphate
Column : Agilent C 18(4.6 x 150mm) 5 μ
Flow rate : 1.0 ml/min
Wavelength : 593 nm
Column temp : Ambient
Sample temp : Ambient
Injection Volume : 10 μ l
Retention time : 7.250 min

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Method validation

1. Linearity

10 mg of Oxcarbazepine working standard was accurately weighed and was transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

2. Accuracy

10mg of Oxcarbazepine working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

3. Specificity

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there is any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The specificity was performed by injecting blank.

4. Precision

4.1 Repeatability

Preparation of stock solution

10 mg of Oxcarbazepine working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

4.2 Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as ruggedness) of the method, precision was performed on different days by using different make column of same dimensions.

5. Limit of detection (LOD)

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

6. Limit of quantification (LOQ)

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

7. Robustness

As part of the robustness, deliberate change in the flow rate, mobile phase composition was made to evaluate the impact on the method.

8. System suitability

10 mg of Oxcarbazepine working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Assay calculation for Oxcarbazepine

Chromatogram showing assay of sample injection- 1, 2, 3

S.NO	NAME	RT	AREA	HEIGHT(μ V)
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.232	896838	124869
2	Oxcarbazepine	7.233	898292	128687
3	Oxcarbazepine	7.234	901496	129200
Mean			898875	
Std.Dev.			2383.1	
%RSD			0.27	

Chromatogram showing standard of sample injection -1, 2, 3.

S.NO	NAME	RT	AREA	HEIGHT(μ V)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxcarbapine	7.235	892717	124236	1.4	3922.9
2	Oxcarbapine	7.236	899298	124029	1.4	3883.2
3	Oxcarbapine	7.237	891366	125525	1.4	4023.9
Mean			894460			
Std.Dev.			4243.6			
%RSD			0.47			

LINEARITY:

S.No	Peak name	Rt	Area
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.412	804543
2	Oxcarbazepine	7.413	932134
3	Oxcarbazepine	7.413	1092224
4	Oxcarbazepine	7.415	1254135
5	Oxcarbazepine	7.416	1403793
	Average		1097366
	SD		215196.4
	%RSD		0.19

Linearity Results for Oxcarbazepine:

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	20 ppm	304543
2	II	40 ppm	602135
3	III	60 ppm	892224
4	IV	80 ppm	1223136
5	V	100 ppm	1503793
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Calibration graph for Oxcarbazepine**ACCURACY:**

%Concentration (at specification level)	Average area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean recovery
50%	1093514.6	5	4.96	99.91%	100.56%
100%	2246802.7	10	9.98	99.18%	
150%	3407885.8	15	15.02	99.60%	

PRECISION:

S.NO	NAME	RT	AREA	HEIGHT(μ V)
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.428	894562	128135
2	Oxcarbazepine	7.429	896754	129139
3	Oxcarbazepine	7.431	893627	132891
4	Oxcarbazepine	7.432	893750	129914
5	Oxcarbazepine	7.433	892682	130515
Mean			894275	
Std.Dev.			1537.7	
%RSD			0.17	

Intermediate precision/Ruggedness

S.NO	NAME	RT	AREA	HEIGHT(μ V)
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.434	895311	125747
2	Oxcarbazepine	7.435	896783	122578
3	Oxcarbazepine	7.436	895237	124365
4	Oxcarbazepine	7.437	894206	124057
5	Oxcarbazepine	7.437	895085	125410
Mean			895324	
Std.Dev.			927.8	
%RSD			0.10	

Detection limit

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOD(μ g/ml)
Oxcarbazepine	1537.7	15205	0303

Quantification limit

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOQ(μ g/ml)
Oxcarbazepine	1537.7	15205	1.011

Robustness

Chromatogram showing less flow rate 0.8ml/min

S.NO	NAME	RT (min)	AERA($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	HEIGHT(μV)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxcarbazine	7.325	10057601	139698	1.4	4921.2

Chromatogram showing more flow rate 1.2 ml/min

S.NO	NAME	RT (min)	AERA($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	HEIGHT(μV)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxcarbazine	7.326	819776	131818	1.4	4493.3

System suitability

S. No	Flow rate (ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	4921	1.4
2	1	4600	1.4
3	1.2	4493	1.4

Chromatogram showing more organic phase ratio

S.NO	NAME	RT (min)	AERA($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	HEIGHT(μV)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.327	922032	143739	1.3	3834.7

Chromatogram showing less organic phase ratio

	NAME	RT (min)	AERA($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	HEIGHT(μV)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Oxcarbazepine	7.328	893128	118935	1.3	5032.7

System suitability results for Oxcarbazepine

S. No	Change in organic composition in the mobile phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	5 % less	5032	1.3
2	*Actual	4522	1.3
3	5 % more	3834	1.3

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Simple reversed-phase HPLC method for analysis of the Oxcarbazepine in rat plasma had been developed and validated. The optimized chromatographic conditions gave optimum baseline separation. The method was found to be linear, precise, accurate and sensitive; thus being suitable for direct analysis of Oxcarbazepine in the laboratory. The method was found to be robust and will enable quality-control analyst to perform preclinical bioavailability studies.

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